

Hriday

A Study based on Vedic Tradition

Sati Shankar
www.satishankar.in

Global Synergetic Foundation, New Delhi, India, 110024
www.globalsynergetic.org

Abstract

Hriday has different connotation to different people, to *Rishis*, it is One or his or her deity, for a physician it is a part of the body, for a poet or a lover, it is the lover. In aesthetics, it is the core of *Rasa*, *Rasika* and *Rasawant*, all at once. In the Vedic tradition it is at the centre stage, right from the very beginning, but unfathomable to not only the common people, but Vedic Rishis or seers. In the Veda, *Hriday* is equated to Divine, *manas*, cosmos both micro and macro, the non-living and living being, and to *Brahman*. Whole of the cosmos is interlinked with the central core, the *Hriday*. Even in Ayurveda and modern medical sciences, *Hriday* has been a controversial issue. With consensus, Brain and *Hriday*, share almost equal claims to be synonymous to *Hriday*. Two *Hriday* have been accepted, namely *UroHriday* and *SiroHriday*, the seat of *Buddhi*, *Manas*, *Chetana* and *Indriya*. It is also proposed that there are two brains, one in cranial cavity and other is situated in *Hriday* itself. Here we take up Rig Veda 10.129.04, from the *Nasadiya Sukta*, one of the most famous hymns on cosmogony, also misleadingly called, the creation hymn as the starting point. The structure of the hymn is such that the verses 1, 6 and 7 put forward unanswered questions on cosmogony and the verses 2 to 5, placed in the middle of the hymn, provoke the wisdom by leading into the, *Hriday* with a view that the seeker will find the answer on his or her own. Sayana /Wilson, rendered it as, " In the beginning there was desire, which was the first seed of *manas*; sages having meditated in their *Hriday* have discovered by their wisdom the connexion of the existent with the non-existent." A careful review of scholarship and interpretation of this hymn during the last few centuries, reveals that the *Manas-Hriday* interaction is still a mystery. To have a deeper insight, a careful study of *Manas-Hriday antahkriya*, as in Vedic tradition, is indispensable. Our knowledge depends on our *jnanendriyas*. Paper ponders in some facts from Rigveda and Ayurveda to lay a few bricks to the bare foundations of the core of Vedic Cosmogony.

Keywords: Hriday, Heart, brain, Manas, Charak, Sushrut, Ayurveda, Rig Veda Hriday Marma, Trimarmsiddhi, Paripalanam, Manas, Roga, Sadhaka Pitta, Manovaha, Sanjnavaha Srotas. Triguna, Tridosha

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Sati Shankar
www.satishankar.in

Global Synergetic Foundation, New Delhi, India, 110024
satigsf@gmail.com, +918130358384, www.globalsynergetic.org

Whereas everyone wants to live in the *Hriday* of some one of his or her choice, be a deity, or the lover, it has been having different connotation to different people, to *Rishis*, it is One or his or her deity, to a physician it is a part of the body, to a poet or a lover, it is the lover. In *Rasa Shastra*, it is the “core intersection space” of *Rasa*, *Rasika* and *Rasawant*, all at once, [1]. In the Vedic tradition it has been at the centre stage, right from the very beginning. Vedic Rishis or seers strived hard to get into it, whereas it has been unfathomable to the common people.

We are confined here to a word which has been used intensively as well as extensively, not only in our Bhartiya Vedic tradition, but also in the prophetic religions, in arts, in literature, in aesthetics and as well as in contemporary life and medical sciences, and surprisingly, nowhere one has been able to say, with confidence, what exactly does it mean. I am talking about something, which is present both, physically and otherwise, and has been the core of life.

Yes, it *Hriday*.

Vedic Hriday craved my attention when I found, as early as in the year 2008, in a survey of interpretations in the Vedic cosmogony, that almost all the interpreters skipped *Hriday*, very cleverly, when they confronted with it in RV.10.129.04. in *Nasadiya Sukta*, RV.10.129,[2], misleadingly called the Creation hymn. The structure of the *Nasadiya Sukta* is such that the verses RV.10.129.01, RV.10.129.06 and RV.10.129.07 put forward unanswered questions on cosmogony and the verses RV.10.129.02 to RV.10.129.05, placed in the middle of the hymn, provoke the wisdom by leading into the, *Hriday* with a view that the seeker will find the answer on his or her own. RV.10.129.04. reads,

*kāmas tād āgre sām avartatādhi mānaso rétaḥ prathamam yád āsīt
sató bāndhum ásati nír avindan hṛdí pratīṣyā kaváyo manīṣā'*

which Sayana /Wilson, rendered as, ‘In the beginning there was *kāmas*, which was the first seed of *manas*; sages having meditated in their *Hriday*, have discovered by their wisdom the connection of the existent with the non-existent.’ A careful review of scholarship and interpretations of this hymn during the last few centuries, reveals that the *Manas-Hriday* interaction is still a mystery, making it necessary to ponder in.

The Vedic “synthesis of knowledge” was based on the postulation of a correspondence between the cosmic, the terrestrial and the physiological, [3]. This equivalence between the cosmic and the physiological, ŚB 8.1.1.6 .2-6, may be the common thread that permeates all the Vedic literature.”, This led to “the development of the scientific method in India, in that age was inspired by some rough parallels between the physical universe and man's physiology,” and to the notion that *if one could understand man fully*, that would eventually lead to the understanding of the universe,’ [4]. Vedas teach us, that the nature has immutable laws, and it is knowable by the *manas*, through empirical inquiry. Each methodological questioning and

design for overlapping areas, phenomenological or otherwise, linguistic as well as artificial are steps toward the same goal. [5] [6] [7]

Paper justifies the theme of this Conference by presenting the facts from the *Vedas*, *Vedāngas* and subsequent Vedic literature by putting the intrinsic mechanisms and the pathways in *Hriday* which have come down to us and are still a mystery and yet to be explored. The scientific trial and error and experimentations have been paving the way to converge our efforts to the designated path of exploration. We shall be dealing with the concept of *Hriday*, intents of its use by the Vedic seers, its application to Ayurveda and its interconnection and interactions with *Manas*, which in turn is Rig Vedic Agni, besides some applications to *Natya Shastra*, *Shaivism*, Buddha's teachings etc, to throw some light on the core position. Keeping the space and occasion limits in view, we shall be synoptic in our presentation. Full comprehension requires intensive Vedic foundation. Details to be made available in author's forthcoming book, *Vedic Agni*.

1. *Hriday in Veda*

To begin systematically, we must have a look at the various but significant associations of *Hriday* since Rig Veda first. To gain insight, we can initially go through the *Rig Vedic Mantras* in which *Hriday* plays a significant role. [8] [9].

In RV. 1.043.01, the *Rishi* intends his *yaja* be pleasant to win the *Hriday* of his deity. "what are we to say to *Rudra*, what is most pleasant to his *Hriday*".

*kād rudrāya prācetase mīl̥hūṣtamāya tāvyase
vocēma śāmtamaṃ hṛdé*

RV. 5.011.05

The *Hriday* is the *organ*, with which one can *see* what is denied to the physical eye. *túbhyedám agne mádhumattamaṃ vācas túbhyam manīṣā́ iyám astu śám̥ hṛdé
tvām̥ gírah̥ síndhum̥ ivāvánīr mahīr̥ ā́ pṛñanti śávasā vardháyanti ca*

RV. 10.064.02. The same organ, *Hriday*, is the place where the *kratavah* are produced and made effective.

*kratūyánti krátavo hṛtsú dhītáyo vénanti venāḥ patáyanty ā́ díṣaḥ
ná marḍitā́ vidyate anyá ebhyo devéṣu me ádhi kāmā́ ayamsata*

RV. 05.085.02), *Varuṇa* places the generative force *vāja*, and laid the faculty called *kratu-* in the *Hriday*.

*vāneṣu vy á lntárikṣam̥ tatāna vājā́m̥ áRV.atsu páya usrīyāsu
hṛtsú krátum̥ vāruṇo apsv á lgnīm̥ diví sū́ryam̥ adadhāt̥ sómam̥ ádrau*

RV.06.009.06. It is the *Hriday* which enables a human being to penetrate deep secrets and mysteries. "my eye is opened, this light dawn (upon me) that is placed in (my) *Hriday*".

*ví me kárñā́ patayato ví cákṣur̥ vīā́ ldam̥ jyótir̥ hṛ́daya ā́hitam̥ yát
ví me mánaṣ̥ carati dūrā́adhīḥ kím̥ svid vakṣyā́mi kím̥ u nū́ maniṣye*

RV. 07.033.09, "they penetrate into the mystery by the perceptions of their *Hriday*".

*tá ín̥ nīnyám̥ hṛ́dayasya prakētáíḥ sahásravalśam̥ abhí́ sám̥ caranti
yaména tatám̥ paridhīm̥ váyanto 'psarása úpa sedur vāsīṣthāḥ*

RV. 01.067.04, Specifies the *dristi*. It is within or by the *Hriday* that the visions are fashioned into words. "they pronounced the sacred texts, and thoughts, which were fashioned by the *Hriday*".

vidántīm átra náro dhiyamdhā́ hṛdā́ yát taṣṭān mántrām áśamsan

RV. 03.039.01, *Indram* which comes into existence from the *Hriday*, from us...".

*índram matír hṛdá á vacyámānāchā pátim stómataṣṭā jigāti
yā jāgrvir vidáthe śasyámānéndra yát te jāyate viddhí tāsya*

RV. 10.71.08, the impulses of the *manas* (=Agni), are said to have been fashioned with the *Hriday*'

*hṛdā́ taṣṭéṣu mánaso javéṣu yád brāhmaṇāḥ saṃyájante sákhāyah
átrāha tvaṃ ví jahur vedyābhir óhabrahmāṇo ví caranty u tve*

RV. 01.061.02, "they refine their 'visions', 'manas' and reflection', for *Indra* with *Hriday*,".

*asmā́ íd u práya iva prá yaṃsi bhárāmy āṅgūśám bādhe suvṛktí
índrāya hṛdā́ mánasā manīṣā́ pratnā́ya pátye dhíyo marjayanta*

RV.08.100.05 Shows the 'co-operation' between the *Hriday* and *manas*, where the *manas* is said to have answered the *Hriday*.

*ā́ yán mā venā́ áruhann ṛtāsyaṃ ékam āsīnam haryatāsya pṛṣṭhé
mánaṣ cin me hṛdá á práty avocad ácikradañ chísumantaḥ sákhāyah*

RV. 04.058.06, tells the process which the visions undergo in the *Hriday*:

*samyák sravanti saríto ná dhénā antár hṛdā́ mánasā pūyámānāḥ
eté arṣanty ūrmáyo ghṛtāsya mṛgā́ iva kṣipañór īsamānāḥ*

RV. 03.026.08, Tracing the 'thought', the light, with or within the *Hriday*, he has made himself, according to his own nature, the highest gem". By finding, with or in the *Hriday*, the light of higher insight and contact with the transcendent one becomes an all-seeing *rṣi*, renders Geldner.

*tribhíḥ pavitrair ápupod dhy a rkām hṛdā́ matím jyótir ánu prajānán
vársiṣṭham rátanam akṛta svadhābhir ā́d íd dyāvāpṛthivī páry apaśyat*

RV.10.177.01, *Hriday* and *Vedic Samudra* are identical. "the inspired ones (*vipascitah*) see the bird (i.e. the light of insight and inspiration) with their *Hriday*; the inspired *kavi* see (it) in the ocean" (*samudre antah*).

*patamgám aktám ásurasya māyáyā́ hṛdā́ paśyanti mánasā vipaścítah
samudré antáh kaváyo ví cakṣate márīcīnām padám ichanti vedhásah*

RV.10.123.6, Soma is addressed as follows: "when they, looking eagerly with their *Hriday* (*Irdā venantah*), saw thee flying up as a bird to the firmament...".

*nāke suparnám úpa yát pátantaṃ hṛdā́ vénanto abhy ácakṣata tvā
híraṇyapakṣam váruṇasya dūtám yamásya yónau śakunám bhuraṇyúm*

RV.1.24.12. The *Hriday* is quite consistently the place from where the expectations are formed, which is equivalent to the opinions of those who "know",

*tád ín náктаṃ tád dívā máhyam áhus tád ayám kéto hṛdá á ví caṣṭe
śúnaḥśépo yám áhavad grbhītáh só asmān rájā́ váruṇo mumoktu*

AV. 9.1.1, It is the same *Hriday* with which people are, in; said to meet the honey-whip of the Asvins.

A.V. 8.18.15 The *Hriday* of men is also considered the place where the Devas enter communication with the human beings.
devā hrtsu jānītha martyam.

The core position that *Hriday* occupies in Vedas can be seen even with these few citations, *Hriday* is equated to the Divine, Agni, manas, cosmos both micro and macro, the non-living and living being, and to *Brahmn*. Whole of the cosmos is interlinked with the central core, the *Hriday* which pervades the whole.

2. *Hriday in AyurVeda*

Most of the studies, interpretations, with whatever stream, grammatical, linguistic, Tantrik, Adhyatmic, hence, all the Vedic, post-Vedic philosophical developments, confine to, or have been heavily based on the knowledge gained by *jnanendriyas*.
śarīramādyam khalu jñānasādhanam [10]

Ayurveda, our ancient science of life believes in the proverb "Prevention Is Better than Cure" as its basic principle. Ayurveda explains the entire human behaviour in terms of *prakriti*. It considers a wide array of factors that determine the *prakriti* of an individual. Ayurveda defines *Prakriti* as "inherent nature" [11]. Also, scholars of Ayurveda define *prakriti* as body characteristics [12], and predominance of *dosha* since birth [13]. This term has an extended use to denote health in the sense of equilibrium of the three biological units of body- the *vata*, *pitta* and *kapha*. The word refers to innate, inherent, or natural rather than disturbed, deviant, or perverted (*vikriti*) state of physical and psychological components [14].

Two types of *prakriti* are described in Ayurveda:

1. *Deha Prakriti* : Categorized based on preponderance of the three biological constitutions of body- *vata*, *pitta*, and *kapha*.

2. *Manasika Prakriti*: *Manasika prakriti* is determined by the relative variation of the three fundamental attributes of *mana* viz. *triguna*- the *suddha*, *rajas* and *tamas* depending upon the dominance of any one of these attributes. The concept of *manasika prakriti* introduces a distinct and new classification of the individual based on the pure psychic features. This classification considers the individual's attitude, orientation, urges, inclinations, temperaments, behavioural patterns, habits, conducts, likings and disliking and many other emotional and intellectual capabilities.

The *rajasika* and *tamasika prakriti* are more prone to psychopathologies due to the presence of *rosha* part and *moha* part respectively [15]. All the factors in balanced form, the "normal", leads to an optimal *prakriti* in an individual. *Dosha*, emerges under disequilibrium.

Further, Ayurveda declares that whichever *dosha* is dominant at the time of union of *shukra* and *shonita*, determine the *prakriti* of an individual [16]. Also dominant *dosha* not only in *shukra* and *shonita* but also due to the effect of *kala* (day of the menstrual period, age of parents or the season), condition of the uterus (*garbhashayaprakriti*) and due to the diet and lifestyle of the mother (*matur-ahara-vihara*) together contribute in the formation of *prakriti* [17].

Ayurveda states 3 basic *marmas*, *Hriday*, *Shira* and *Basti*. Out of these *Marma*, *Hriday* is one of the most important, which is also a *Pranayatana* and *Moolsthan* of *Rasa* and *Rakta Vaha Srotas*.

Hence our ancient science recommends the *Hriday Marma Paripalanam*, which makes protection and nourishment of *Hriday Marma* is most important to prevent *vyadhi*. [18]

Hriday is an Important *Marma* as explained in Ayurvedic Samhitas. It is *sthan* for *Vyan Vayu*, *Sadhak Pitta*, *Avalambak Kaph* and *Ojas* [19].

3. *Hriday Manas Indriya in Ayurveda*

Ayurveda speaks of five *Indriya-Buddhis* with five correlated *Buddhindriyas*. The events in the phenomenal world are intimated through the *Buddhindriyas* to the *IndriyaBuddhis*. Subsequent information processing leading to knowledge, are dealt within cerebral cortex. If the mind have any meaning apart from the behavior of the organism, they are clearly more closely connected with the cerebral cortex than with any other part of the body. [20] *Hriday* is a specified organ for *manovyadhi* comparable to eyes as the sense organ for sight. [21]

There has been a controversy regarding the *Sthana* of *Manas* in Ayurveda and in the Modern medical sciences as well. *Hriday* and *Mastiska* have been the points of discussion since a long, as the location of consciousness and of *Manas*. Ayurvedic definitions use synonyms. The words *Citta*, *Hriday* and *Manas* are said to have the same sense. Similarly, *Manas*, *Sattva* and *Ceta* are synonyms. Caraka holds that *Saguna Atma*, *Ceta* *Manas* and its *Arthas* are seated in *Hriday*. To Susruta and Vagbhata, location of *Sattva* is *Hriday*, which is situated at '*Stanayormadhya*'. Both Caraka and Susruta consider *Hriday* to be the seat of *chetan* in the body. [22] [23]

Hriday is the first organ to form in *Garbhhotpatti*, says Vagbhata, and that is the location of *sattva* which lies in the region of *stanayormadhya*. Cakrapani also opines that *Manas* is in *Hriday*. Acarya Charaka says that *Prana* as situated in *Siras*, also called as *Uttamangam* due to its control over all the *Indriyas* [24].

Manas (= *Vedic Agni=Prajapati=Vac*) is one of the *Prana* and *Indriya* also.

In Harita Samhita, the seat of '*cheta*' is said to reside in *Bhrumadhya* at the upper part of *Nasa*. *Tantrikas* support this view by considering *Ajna Cakra* in *Bhrumadhya* to be the seat of *Manas*.

Vagbhata, in context of the *Marma Viddha Laksanas* mentions 'Manonasa' caused by injury on *Simanta Marma*, *Sirah Sandhi*, lying in *Sirah*, thereby purporting that *Manas* is seated in *Sirah*.

Quite distinct from the traditional thinking in Ayurveda, the Bhela Samhita, regards *Manas* and '*chitt*' as two different entities and says *Manas* is located between *Siras* and *Talu* and it is *Sarvendriyapara*, i.e., the controller of all *Indriyas*, while *Citt* resides in *Hriday*.

While describing the *Srotas*, Caraka mentions *tridosha*, and purports that the *Manas* provides *Chetan* to all the living cells of the body, and hence practically *Manas* pervades all the *Indriya* of the body. Charaka calls *Manas* as *Atindriyam* and the whole body as its *Adhistanam*.

Further, *Manas* is said to have *Samavayi Sambandha* with *Sparsanendriya* hence is able to keep contact with external environment. *Manas* is also considered as *Achetana*. It is under the control of *Atma*, having *chetanatvam*, entering different *Yonis*. As *Manas* follows *Atma*, it does not have a definite location.

In brief, it can be concluded that the primary place of *Manas* can be *Hriday*. It is however stated in Charaka Samhita that the entire sentient body represents the abode of *Manas* and therefore should be considered as the *Manovahasrotas*. [25] [26]

According to Sushruta, the word *Sanjna* indicates knowledge, understanding, hint, sign, mind etc. Since the word *Sanjna* also means *Manas*, in this context, Chakrapani states that the *Sajnavahasrotas* are the *Manovahasrotas*. [27]

Two important functions of *Vata* and *Gandhana* are performed by *Chestavaha Srotas*. The direction of action is from *Buddhi* to *Manas* before reaching the target *Indriya*, *Manas* and *Buddhi* are *Mulas* of the *Chestavaha Srotas*. *Chestavaha Srotas* originate in the *Buddhi* and pass through the *Manas* to spread throughout the body. Hence all the organs function under the supervision and incitement of the *Manas* and *Buddhi*. The *Manovahasrotas* are cohesively interlinked to interact with the *Sajnavahasrotas* which extend from the sense organs to the *Manas* and *Chestavahasrotas*. Therefore, the *Manovahasrotas* seem to have spread throughout the body, with *Manas* and *Buddhi* being the *Mula*.

Acarya Charaka does not make any direct mention of *Sadhaka Pitta* but throws light on some of the functions ascribed to it in general. [28]

Chakrapanidatta, however, describes this *Pitta* and identified its location, *Hriday*. It gives rise to *saurya*, *bhaya*, *rodha*, *harsa*, *moha* and hence *manovyadhi*. Susruta and Vagbhata have both made direct mention of *Sadhaka Pitta*. To Acarya Susruta, the *Pitta* located in *Hriday* is to be known as the *Sadhakagni*, in as much as its function is to enable one to achieve one's *Manoratha* by *purushartha*. Dalhana observe that it enables one to achieve one's *Manoratha*, *Dharma*, *Artha*, *Kama* and *Moksa*. Which is done by it by dispelling the *Kapha* and *Tamas* of the *Hriday* and thus enables the *Manas* to perceive things clearly. Astanga Samgraha states that as *Sadhaka Pitta* is in *Hriday*, it is responsible for *Buddhi Medha*, *Utsaha* and the achievement of one's *manoratha*. Similarly, in Astanga *Hriday*, again *Pitta* is said to be in the *Hriday* and attributed to it is *Buddhi*, *Medha*, *Abhimana* and the capacity of *purushartha*.

The tridosha, moves through *Dhamani* and affects *Hriday* which cause abnormal function causing ultimately *manovyadhi*. [29]

Acharya Charaka says, *Dosas* cause the *Satwaguna* having been obscured by *Tamo* and *Rajo Gunas*, the *Hriday* becomes involved by *Prakupita Dosas*. *Manas* being oppressed with worry, manifests itself in *Apasmara*. The *Prakupita Dosas* involve *Hriday* via *Dhamanis* and impairs its functions. [30]

Describing the condition known as *Atatwabhinivesha* Charaka says, when the *Manas* is enveloped by *Rajas* and *Moha* in *Hriday*, it impairs the pathways of the *Manas* and understanding become enveloped by *Rajas* and *Moha* and gets further disturbed by the rampant *Dosas*. [31]

The *Sharira Dosas* of the weak-minded (*Alpasatwa*) becoming impaired vitiates the *Hriday* which is the seat of *Manas*, get localized in the *Manovaha-srotas* and soon disturbs the functions of the *Manas*. [32]

Manas in *Hriday* is the Master of all the *Indriyas* and *Vayu* is the master of *Manas* (*Hathayoga Pradipika*). Acarya Bhela says "*Manas* is enclosed between the *Shiras* and *Talu*. It is *Sarvendriyapara* i.e., the controller of all *Indriyas*. It receives the sensation, *Rasa*, *Gandha*,

Sparsa and *Sabda*. It thus becomes conscious of its surroundings holistically. The power of all *Indriyas* is derived from *Manas*. The cause of different modes of functioning of the *buddhi* is *Chitt*, which is in *Hriday* and *Chitt* is also the basis of all other functions. The *Sadhaka Pitta* appears to be psycho-physiological in its outlook. A proper appreciation of it depends upon a clear understanding of the implications of the terms *Hrid* or *Hriday*. *Cheta*, *Swantam*, *Hrit* and *Manas* are the synonyms of *Hriday*. The location of this organ in the *Uras* has been described by Acaryas, especially Susruta. [33]

Hriday is now recognized by scientists as an overly complex system with its own functional brain. It is also clear that heart and brain have functional similarity and Ayurvedic science has described functions of *Hriday* which is quite close to the other. Ayurveda described brain and heart under one closure the *Hriday*, therefore, in addition to circulation of blood *Hriday* works as brain also.

4. *Hriday, Vedic Agni and Manas*

Having seen the basic mechanism present in *Hriday* with respect to *Manasa*, *Triguna* and *Tridoshas*, it is now time to revert once again to RigVada, to explore some links between Vedic *Agni*, *Manas*, *Hriday*. This section is brief, space falls short here, as said, full comprehension requires intensive foundational details and shall be available in author's forthcoming book, *Vedic Agni*.

In the words of S B 10.5.3.3, Agni should be, *manasalvddhiyanta manasaciyanta*, "laid by *Manas* and edified by *Manas*", because *Agni* Himself performs "*manasa yaja*" *manasd yajati*, Now, RV1.077.02, for, one who would attain to Him as "like to like" must have done likewise, without which it would have been impossible. *Manas*, in the *Vedic Samhitas* and *Brahmanas*, and sometimes in the *Upanisads*, is the Pure or Possible *Manas*.
yó adhvaréṣu śámtama ṛtāvā hótā tám ū námobhir ā kṛṇudhvam
agnír yád vér mártāya devān sá cā bódhāti mánasā yajāti

Thus RV 1.139.02 says,

yád dha tyán mitrávaruṇāv ṛtād ádhy ādadāthe ánṛtaṃ svéna manyúnā dáksasya svéna manyúnā
yuvór itthādhi sádmasv ápaśyāma hiraṇyáyam dhībhīś caná mánasā svébhír akśábhīḥ sómasya
svébhír akśábhīḥ

and with RV 1.145.02,

tám ít pṛchanti ná simó ví pṛchati svéneva dhīro mánasā yád ágrabhīt
ná mṛsyate prathamám nāparam váco 'syá krátvā sacate ápradrpitaḥ

"What He [*Agni*], contemplative, ...grasped by His own *Manas*"; *sveneva Aim manasd yad agrabhīt*. *Manojavas* is a name of *Agni*, JB 1.50 and TS 11.5.11.5, "*Manas* is virtually *Prajapati*" (*mana iva hi prajdpatih*) and then *Manas*, as in SB 10.5.3.1 4, is identified with as in, (RV 10.129.01), "That which was in the beginning neither Non being nor Being"

nāsad āsīn nó sád āsīt tadānīm nāsīd rájo nó vyo lmā paró yát
kím āvarīvaḥ kúha kásya śármann ámbhaḥ kím āsīd gáhanam gabhīrám

This *Manas*, emanates the *Vac*, (*vacam asrjata*), a function usually assigned to *Prajapati*. On it, BU 1.5.7, declares, "The Father is *Manas*; and so is The Mother, *Vac*; the Child, Spirit or Life *prana*," the Knower and the Known, are the universal parents of the conceptual universe,

and therefore, as in KU.iv.ii, "He, *Manas*, is attainable through *Manas*."(*manasaivedam aptavyam*), in the *Hridaya*.

Hence the equivalence, *Hridaya*=*Manas* = *Vedic Agni*=*Prajapati*=*Vac* is one of the *Prana* and *Indriya*. QED

5. *Hridaya* in other Contexts [34]

In *Natyashastra Hridaya* is a type of glance, unsteady, flurried, the pupils moving somewhat (*anaglulita*)

In *Matsya Purāna*, *Hridaya* from neck to heart is 12 *aṅgulas*.

In *Purana* and *Itihasa*:

Śivapurāṇa 2.2.2.: *Hridaya* refers to the "*Hridaya*" of Śiva from which Rudra was born, ..*Brahmā* said, "Originally when Śiva was separated from Śakti and was pure consciousness alone, He was attributeless, free from alternatives, devoid of forms and beyond the existent and non-existent. [...] Viṣṇu was born of His (*vāmāṅga*) and I, *Brahmā*, of his (*dakṣiṅāṅga*), O great sage, Rudra was born of his (*Hridaya*). I became the creator (*Brahmā*); Viṣṇu the cause of sustenance; Rudra the author of dissolution. Thus *Sadāśiva*, manifested himself in three forms".

Śivapurāṇa 2.2.16 says, *The Paramātma ... Śiva manifests in three different ways due to Māyā. The lord is independent in his divine sports. Viṣṇu was born of His (*vāmāṅga*) and I, Brahṁā, of his (*dakṣiṅāṅga*), You are born of the (*Hridaya*) of Śiva and are his full-fledged incarnation. Thus, O lord, we have become three, with different forms. We are the sons of Śivā and Śiva which, O eternal one, you must note".*

In Śivapurāṇa 2.2.30 *Hridaya* refers to the "*hrid kshetra*", where *Satī* stabilized the *udāna* while in a yogic trance. *Brahmā* narrates to *Nārada*, "[...] She (*Satī*) then entered the yogic *sthitī*. Keeping her face steady, she balanced the *Prāṇa* and *Apāna* [i.e., *prāṇāpāna*]. She then lifted the *Udāna* from the umbilical region, stabilised it in the *hrid kshetra* (*Hridaya*)

In *Vastu Shastra*,

Mānasāra LXX, 111. *Hridaya* exhorts the *sthapati* and the *sthāpaka* to install the image in the sanctuary of their *Hridaya* as well.

Hridaya is a Sanskrit technical term used in ancient Indian sciences such as *Astronomy*, *Mathematics* and *Geometry*. In *Jyotisha*, *Hridaya* refers to the *Circum-radius*.

In *Mahayana Buddhism*:

Visuddhimagga, *Hridaya* (*Pali*, *Hadaya*) refers to one of the thirty-substances of the human body.

The *Mahāprajñāpāramitāśāstra* chapter 32-34. mentions thirty-six substances [viz., *Hridaya*].

In *Tibetan Buddhism*

Vajrayana or *tantric Buddhism*: *Hridaya* (हृदय) is the name of a *Vākchomā* ('verbal secret sign') which has its meaning defined as 'vīra' according to chapter 8 of the 9th-century *Vajradākamahātantrarāja*

Hridaya and its derivatives in Dictionaries have not been assembled here.

6. Way forward

The pointers assembled here are sufficient to show the significance of *Hriday*, not only in Vedic tradition but for the modern scientific developments. The intricate causalities, linkages, and internetworking within *Hriday* and its coordinates put its study at the forefront. *Hriday* is equated to Divine, *manas*, cosmos both, micro and macro, the non-living and living being, and to *Brahman*. “With the equivalence, *Hriday=Manas = Vedic Agni=Prajapati=Vac is one of the Prana and Indriya*” the whole of the cosmos is interlinked with the central core, the *Hriday*. Even in Ayurveda and modern medical sciences, *Hriday*, its *Astitva*, *prakriti*, *pravriti* and its *mooladhaar* still remains a controversial issue, and requires pondering in. *Hriday*, pragmatically speaking, is like the black box which has confined within itself the whole with the forces and intricate mechanisms of not only the cosmogony but of its existence itself.

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